

DELIVERABLE

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Authors:

Raffaella Santucci (QED)
Vincenzo Grillo (CNR)
Luca Marco Carlo Giberti (QED)
Gian Carlo Gazzadi (CNR)

Contributors:

Reviewers:

Vittore Casarosa (CNR-ISTI, OPEN UP Project)
Paolo Manghi (CNR-ISTI, OPENAIRE/OPENAIRE ADVANCE Projects)

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1 Introduction	6
1.1 Open Data and Open Access in H2020 and in Q-SORT	6
1.2 Objectives of the Q-SORT Project	8
2. Q-SORT Data Types	8
2.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	8
2.2 What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?	9
2.3 Will you re-use any existing data and how?	9
2.4 What is the origin of the data?	9
2.5 What is the expected size of the data?	9
2.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?	9
3 Making Data FAIR	9
3.1 Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable data	10
3.2 How Q-SORT will promote data sharing and re-use	11
3.2.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	11
3.2.2 When will the data be made available for re-use?	11
3.2.3 Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	11
3.2.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	11
3.3 Data protection	11
3.4 Open Access Publications	13
4 Allocation of resources	21
4.1 What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project? How will these be covered? Note that costs related to open access to research data are eligible as part of the Horizon 2020 grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)	21
4.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?	22
5 Open data security	22
5.1 What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)?	22
5.2 Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long-term preservation and curation?	22
6 Ethical aspects	23
6.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review.	23
7 List of Q-SORT data sets, pre-prints, articles, deliverables published on ZENODO	23

8 Conclusion	25
ANNEX 1 - EXPERIMENTAL DATA SET SPECIFICATIONS	26
ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS	27
Short Name Of Participants	27
List Of Abbreviations	27

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Europe 2020 strategy for a smart, sustainable, and inclusive economy underlines the central role of knowledge and innovation in generating growth. For this reason, the European Union strives to improve access to scientific information and to boost the benefits of public investment in the research funded under the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon 2020 (2014-2020).

According to this strategy, in Horizon 2020 a limited pilot action on open access to research data has been implemented so that participating projects will be required to develop an Open Data Management Plan (ODMP), in which they will specify what data will be open.

This updated version of the deliverable of the Q-SORT project is prepared as part of WP1, Open Data Management Plan (Update). In this document we update the discussion regarding the management, life cycle, processes of data generated by Q-SORT in order to make such data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR).

The aim of this document is to provide an analysis of the main elements of the data management policy that will be used with regard to all the data sets that will be generated by the project.

In particular, the deliverable outlines how research data will be handled during the lifetime of Q-SORT and describes what data will be collected, processed or generated and what methodology will be followed, whether and how this data will be shared and/or made open, and how it will be curated and preserved.

This data management plan is intended as a dynamic document that will be edited and updated during the project.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 OPEN DATA AND OPEN ACCESS IN H2020 AND IN Q-SORT

In December 2013, the European Commission announced their commitment to open data through the Pilot on Open Research Data, as part of the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme¹. The Pilot's aim is to *"improve and maximise access to and re-use of research data generated by projects for the benefit of society and the economy"*.

In the frame of the Pilot on Open Research Data, results of publicly-funded research should be disseminated more broadly and faster, for the benefit of researchers, innovative industry and citizens².

On one hand, Open Access accelerates discovery processes and makes it easier for research results to reach the market (thus meaning higher returns on public investment), and also avoids duplication of research efforts, thus leading to a better use of public resources. On the other hand, this Open Access policy is also beneficial for the researchers themselves. Making the research publicly available increases the visibility of the performed research, which translates into a higher number of citations³ as well as an increase in the collaboration potential with other institutions in new projects, among others. Additionally, Open Access offers small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) access to the latest research for utilisation.

Under H2020, each beneficiary must ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. These open access requirements are based on a balanced support to both 'Green open access' (immediate or delayed open access that is provided through self-archiving) and 'Gold open access' (immediate open access that is provided by a publisher).

Apart from open access to publications, projects must also aim to deposit the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications, known as "underlying data". In order to effectively supply this data, projects need to consider at an early stage how they are going to manage and share the data they create or generate. In addition, beneficiaries must ensure their research data are findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR)⁴.

In this document, we will introduce the first version of the Open Data Management Plan (ODMP) elaborated for the Q-SORT project. The ODMP describes how to select, structure, store, and make public the information used or generated during the project, both considering scientific publications as well as generated research data. The Q-SORT ODMP follows the ODMP structure given by the ODMPonline tool⁵ as suggested in the EC ODMP template.

We anticipate here that Q-SORT, as a best practice, will make use of the ZENODO⁶ repository (an OpenAIR⁷ and CERN collaboration).

The reasons to use this repository are the following:

- it allows researchers to deposit both publications and data, while providing tools to link them;
- in order to increase visibility and impact of the project the Q-SORT Community has been created in ZENODO, so all beneficiaries of the project can link the uploaded paper to the Community;
- the repository has backup and archiving capabilities;
- ZENODO assigns all publicly available uploads a unique Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for citation;
- it makes the upload easy;
- the repository allows different access rights.

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

² http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

³ "There is evidence that studies that make their data available do indeed receive more citations than similar studies that do not." Piwowar H. and Vision T.J 2013 "Data reuse and the open data citation advantage" <https://peerj.com/preprints/1.pdf>

⁴ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

⁵ <https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/>

⁶ <https://zenodo.org>

⁷ <https://www.openaire.eu>

Community URLs ▾

Collection URL: <https://zenodo.org/communities/qsort/>
Above address links directly to your community collection.

Upload URL: <https://zenodo.org/deposit/new?c=qsort>
Above address will automatically ensure people who use it will have their record added to your community collection.

Curation URL: <https://zenodo.org/communities/qsort/curate/>
Above address links to your private curation URL. You will find all uploads pending your curation.

Harvesting URL: [Zenodohttps://zenodo.org/oai2d?verb=ListRecords&set=user-qsort&metadataPrefix=oai_dc](https://zenodo.org/oai2d?verb=ListRecords&set=user-qsort&metadataPrefix=oai_dc)
Above address links to a OAI-PMH feed, which can be used by other digital repositories to harvest this community.

Figure 1 - Screenshot of the Zenodo repository

The screenshot shows the Zenodo repository interface. At the top is a blue header with the Zenodo logo, a search bar, and links for 'Upload' and 'Communities'. Below the header, the date 'June 19, 2018' is displayed, along with 'Figure' and 'Open Access' tags. The main title is 'Q-SORT - Group Photo+Logo' with the identifier 'QED'. The description reads: 'Q-SORT and DIP projects held an international conference on electron beam shaping in Jülich (Germany) - Group photo 1 + Logo (overlaid)'. A 'Preview' section shows a group photo of people in an auditorium, with the 'Q-SORT' logo overlaid in large red letters.

Figure 2 -Zenodo Repository/Q-SORT Community - Sample upload

This ODMF will be updated during the project lifetime.

1.2 OBJECTIVES OF THE Q-SORT PROJECT

Q-SORT introduces a revolutionary concept whereby the transmission electron microscope (TEM) is employed as a so-called Quantum Sorter, i.e. a device that is able to pick out and display detailed information about electron quantum states. This in turn provides researchers with precious new information about the sample being examined.

The project -which includes applications in physics, biology, and biochemistry- is expected to have a wide-ranging impact due to the ubiquitous adoption of TEM and STEM across many disciplines. Indeed, strong interdisciplinarity, featuring a multi-year collaboration between physicists and biologists, is one of Q-SORT's defining traits. The project features a strong international consortium with potential industrial applications.

Q-SORT also has foundational value in physics as it fosters its own kind of sparse-sensing approach to TEM, advancing the field in the direction of quantum measurement. Intuitively, sparse sensing is analogous to how we recognise familiar people from just a few small details: it means that only a few measurements are taken compared to traditional approaches – yet these are still sufficient to extract all the relevant information. A similar thing happens when we recognise relatives just from their silhouette or profile or any other small detail: we don't need to see their full face to identify them.

The scientific and technical results of the Q-SORT project are expected to be of maximum interest for the scientific community.

2. Q-SORT DATA TYPES

As previously noted, the Q-SORT project is an H2020 Research and Innovation Action, and hence will generate scientific data - however the current plan addresses also the data produced as a result of the Communication and Public Engagement activities of the project.

2.1 WHAT IS THE PURPOSE OF THE DATA COLLECTION/GENERATION AND ITS RELATION TO THE OBJECTIVES OF THE PROJECT?

The stated Q-SORT project breakthroughs and objectives are:

Breakthroughs:

A novel 'quantum toolbox' will be developed to enable the following breakthroughs in advanced characterisation and analysis:

- B1. A general theoretical framework to tailor the Quantum Sorter to a basis of choice.
- B2. The application of the Quantum Sorter to the measurement of atomically-resolved magnetic dichroism.
- B3. Characterisation of the dispersion relation between plasmon energy and orbital angular momentum (OAM) in spherical nanoscale objects¹ (fullerenes and Au nanoparticles).
- B4. A proof-of-concept application of the Quantum Sorter for the direct identification of individual proteins and their orientations using at least one order of magnitude fewer electrons .

Objectives:

- To design and fabricate novel electromagnetic (e.-m.) phase-shifting elements that are capable of dynamically controlling the sorting of the wavefunction of the electron beam according to its OAM (T2.3, T2.4, T2.5).
- To develop a theoretical framework of physically sparse sensing via optimised basis change (T3.1, T3.2). To develop holograms and tunable phase modulators based on e.-m. elements (T3.3, T3.4).
- To study nanoscale magnetic properties with improved signal to noise over present technology (T4.2, T4.4).

- To study for the first time the OAM signatures of plasmonic excitations in chosen nanostructures (T4.1, T4.3).
- To develop 'safe' (low-dose or 'minimally destructive') measurement techniques aimed at revealing the orientations of single proteins, as well as the characteristic symmetries and motifs of molecules (WP5).

Data collection and generation related to each of the above serves to enable the realisation, effective achievement, and evaluation of the Q-SORT breakthroughs and to effect scientific reporting of research and innovation that will result in each of the objectives.

2.2 WHAT TYPES AND FORMATS OF DATA WILL THE PROJECT GENERATE/COLLECT?

The project will generate and collect the following types and formats of data:

- The experimental data, encapsulating associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications (underlying data).

More specifically, .dm3 files are generated by the TEM machines in Q-SORT. This is a proprietary format from Gatan, which however is quite well documented. Dm3 has its own metadata embedded in the files, which usually consists of: microscope name, date, if necessary user name and technical data such as calibration parameters. We have code to extract this metadata if it is requested. The .dm3 file format can be used to store spectrum (1D), image (2D), and spectral imaging (2D x 1D) information. Simulation data can be also transformed to .dm3 by using the STEM_CELL software.

- The Dissemination and Public Engagement data (webinars, videos, print materials, etc). These consist of common graphic-asset containers such as .mp4 and .pdf files.

2.3 WILL YOU RE-USE ANY EXISTING DATA AND HOW?

Q-SORT will not be re-using any existing data.

2.4 WHAT IS THE ORIGIN OF THE DATA?

The experimental data originates from TEM experiments, part of the original research which is at the core of Q-SORT.

2.5 WHAT IS THE EXPECTED SIZE OF THE DATA?

The expected amount of experimental data generated varies depending on whether experiments are running or not and on how many trials are required. A rough estimate of the experimental data produced during the project is 5 GB (gigabytes).

2.6 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

The Q-SORT project data might be useful:

- to any researcher willing to retry the analysis routines or to test against their own results;
- to academics and university departments and institutes that could use the Q-SORT data for scholarship and teaching purposes;
- to the private sector (industry) for the same above two reasons.

3 MAKING DATA FAIR

Q-SORT partner CNR will regularly upload the above-described experimental data on **Zenodo**⁸. 12 months of embargo between data production and data upload into Zenodo will be enforced in order to allow researchers sufficient time to elaborate and study experimental data, to re-run experiments, to write and publish articles based on such data before the latter is shared publicly.

⁸ <http://about.zenodo.org>

Dissemination and Public Engagement data (logos, videos, graphic assets, etc.) will also be made available to download from Zenodo or from the Q-SORT website (www.qsort.eu).

3.1 FINDABLE, ACCESSIBLE, INTEROPERABLE, REUSABLE DATA

Zenodo embraces the FAIR Principles as defined in *Wilkinson, M. D. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Sci. Data 3:160018 doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18 (2016)*⁹:

“To be Findable:

- **F1:** (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
 - A DOI is issued to every published record on Zenodo.
- **F2:** data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
 - Zenodo's metadata is compliant with [DataCite's Metadata Schema](#) minimum and recommended terms, with a few additional enrichments.
- **F3:** metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes
 - The DOI is a top-level and a mandatory field in the metadata of each record.
- **F4:** (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource
 - Metadata of each record is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing.
 - Metadata of each record is sent to DataCite servers during DOI registration and indexed there.

To be Accessible:

- **A1:** (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol
 - Metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the [OAI-PMH](#) protocol by the record identifier and the collection name.
 - Metadata is also retrievable through the public [REST API](#).
- **A1.1:** the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
 - See point A1. OAI-PMH and REST are open, free and universal protocols for information retrieval on the web.
- **A1.2:** the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
 - Metadata are publicly accessible and licensed under public domain. No authorization is ever necessary to retrieve it.
- **A2:** metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available
 - Data and metadata will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.
 - Metadata are stored in high-availability database servers at CERN, which are separate to the data itself.

To be Interoperable:

- **I1:** (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
 - Zenodo uses [JSON Schema](#) as internal representation of metadata and offers export to other popular formats such as [Dublin Core](#) or [MARCXML](#).
- **I2:** (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
 - For certain terms we refer to open, external vocabularies, e.g.: license ([Open Definition](#)), funders ([FundRef](#)) and grants ([OpenAIRE](#)).
- **I3:** (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data
 - Each referenced external piece of metadata is qualified by a resolvable URL.

To be Reusable:

- **R1:** (meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
 - Each record contains a minimum of DataCite's mandatory terms, with optionally additional DataCite recommended terms and Zenodo's enrichments.

⁹ <http://about.zenodo.org/principles/>

- **R1.1:** (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
 - License is one of the mandatory terms in Zenodo's metadata, and is referring to a [Open Definition](#) license.
 - Data downloaded by the users is subject to the license specified in the metadata by the uploader.
- **R1.2:** (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
 - All data and metadata uploaded is traceable to a registered Zenodo user.
 - Metadata can optionally describe the original authors of the published work.
- **R1.3:** (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards
 - Zenodo is not a domain-specific repository, yet through compliance with DataCite's Metadata Schema, metadata meets one of the broadest cross-domain standards available.

3.2 How Q-SORT WILL PROMOTE DATA SHARING AND RE-USE

Answers to the following questions help to achieve FAIR data.

3.2.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

Q-SORT will share data using Creative Commons licenses (see <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/>). More specifically:

- experimental data will be shared under the Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike CC license (CC BY-NC-SA);
- Dissemination and Public Engagement data will be shared under the Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs CC license (CC BY-NC-ND).

3.2.2 When will the data be made available for re-use?

12 months of embargo between data production and data upload into Zenodo will be enforced in order to allow researchers sufficient time

- to elaborate and study experimental data
- to re-run experiments if necessary
- to write and publish articles based on such data

before the latter is shared it publicly. This allocation of time is realistic since it takes into account machine downtime and availability, as well as experiment duration.

3.2.3 Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes. Data generated by Q-SORT can be used by third parties to verify independently the analysis routines or to test against their own results. It could also, conceivably, be used in aggregate for big data meta-analysis of TEM studies.

3.2.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

For as long as Zenodo exists.

3.3 DATA PROTECTION

Q-SORT data protection aspects will be coordinated according to the recommendations of the relevant national data protection authorities. The project is aware of the new European data protection rules that have entered into force in May 2018 and their impact will be considered:

http://ec.europa.eu/justice/data-protection/reform/index_en.htm

H2020 open access policy stipulates that the information generated by the projects participating in that programme is made publicly available. However, as stated in EC guidelines on Data Management in H2020:¹⁰

¹⁰ EC document: "Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020" – versión 1.0 – 11 December, 2013

As an exception, the beneficiaries do not have to ensure open access to specific parts of their research data if the achievement of the action's main objective, as described in Annex I, would be jeopardised by making those specific parts of the research data openly accessible. In this case, the data management plan must contain the reasons for not giving access.

In line with this, Q-SORT shall decide which data is made public according to aspects such as potential liabilities to commercialisation of technologies, related IPR protection (by patents or other forms of protection), risks with respect to achieving project objectives/outcomes, etc.

Q-SORT entails pioneering research that is of key importance to physics, biology/biochemistry, quantum information manipulation, materials science, optics. Effective exploitation of Q-SORT research results depends on the proper management of intellectual property. To this end, the Q-SORT Consortium will adopt the following strategy (Figure 1):

Figure 1: Process for determining which information is to be made public (from EC's document "Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020 – v1.0 – 11 December 2013")

If the research findings result in innovation or in significant new insights, the members of the consortium will consider two alternatives regarding protection, i.e.:

- to withhold the data for internal use or to apply for a patent in order to commercially exploit the invention and have in return financial gain; in the latter case, related publications will be therefore delayed until the patent filing;
- if said developments are not going to be withheld or patented, to publish results for knowledge-sharing purposes.

All intended dissemination or protection policies and actions are regulated by the Q-SORT Consortium Agreement. Once the relevant protections (e.g. IPR) are secured, Q-SORT partners may disseminate (subject to their legitimate interests) the obtained results and knowledge to the relevant scientific communities through contributions in journals and international conferences in the fields of physics, biochemistry, materials science, etc.

3.4 OPEN ACCESS PUBLICATIONS

The first aspect to be considered in the ODMF is related to open access (OA) to the publications generated within the Q-SORT project, meaning that any peer-reviewed scientific publication made within the context of the project will be available online to any user at no charge. This aspect is mandatory for new projects in the Horizon 2020 programme (article 29.2 of the Model Grant Agreement).

The two alternatives recommended by the EC to comply with this requirement are:

- Self-archiving / 'green' OA: In this option, the beneficiaries deposit the final peer-reviewed manuscript in a repository of their choice. In this case, they must ensure open access to the publication within a maximum of six months (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities).
- Open access publishing / 'gold' OA: In this option, researchers publish their results in open access journals, or in journals that sell subscriptions and also offer the possibility of making individual articles openly accessible via the payment of author processing charges (APCs) (hybrid journals). Again, open access via the chosen repository must be ensured upon publication.

Publications arising from the Q-SORT project will be made public preferably through the option of 'gold' OA in order to provide the widest dissemination of the published results through the own webpages of the publishers. In other cases, the scientific publications will be deposited in a repository ('green' OA). Most publishers allow to deposit a copy of the article in a repository, sometimes with a period of restricted access (embargo)¹¹. In Horizon 2020, the embargo period imposed by the publisher must be shorter than 6 months (or 12 months for social sciences and humanities). This embargo period will be therefore taken into account by the Q-SORT consortium to choose the open access modality for the fulfilment of the open access obligations established by the EC.

Additionally, according to the EC recommendation, whenever possible the Q-SORT consortium will retain the ownership of the copyright for their work through the use of a 'License to Publish', which is a publishing agreement between author and publisher. With this agreement, authors can retain copyright and the right to deposit the article in an Open Access repository, while providing the publisher with the necessary rights to publish the article. Additionally, to ensure that others can be granted further rights for the use and reuse the work, the Q-SORT consortium may ask the publisher to release the paper under a Creative Commons license, preferably CC-0 or CC-BY .

Besides these two facts (retaining the ownership of the publication and effecting an embargo period), the Q-SORT consortium will also consider the relevance of the journal where the paper is intended to be published. Q-SORT aims and is expected to publish results in high impact-factor journals. Therefore, also this aspect will be taken into consideration when selecting the journals in which to publish the Q-SORT project results.

The following is a list of the journals which will be considered for the Q-SORT publications, with information about the open access policy of each journal.

¹¹ <http://www.sherpa.ac.uk/romeo/>

Publisher	Link	Comments about open access
AIP	https://publishing.aip.org/librarians/open-access-policy	A paid open access option is available for this journal. If funding rules apply, publishers version/PDF may be used on author's personal website, institutional website or institutional repository
APS	https://journals.aps.org/pr/edannounce/PhysRevLett.101.140001	The APS gives rights to its authors to use their articles as they wish. The APS has allowed authors the right to publish the APS-prepared, final, and definitive version of the article on their web site or on the authors' institution's web site, immediately upon publication. The author's final version could also be put onto e-print servers such as the arXiv. Authors and their institutions could make copies of their articles for classroom use, and others could copy the article for noncommercial use. They recommend that if authors wish to post a complete article from an APS journal, they instead provide a link to our site, or to a free copy of the article on their personal web sites.
Science	http://www.sciencemag.org/authors/science-journals-editorial-policies	<p>Immediately after publication, authors may post the accepted version of the paper on their personal or institutional archival website. In addition, one author is provided a "referrer" link, which can be posted on a personal or institutional web page and through which users can freely access the final, published paper on the Science Journal's website.</p> <p>For research papers created under grants for which the authors are required by their funding agencies to make their research results publicly available (for example, from NIH, Howard Hughes Medical Institute, or Wellcome Trust), Science allows posting of the accepted version of research content (Research Articles and Reports) to the funding body's archive or designated repository (such as PubMed Central) no sooner than six months after publication, provided that a link to the final version of the paper published in the Science Journal is included. The accepted version is the version of the paper accepted for publication after changes resulting from peer review, but before editing by the Science Journal copyediting staff, image quality control, and production of the final PDF.</p> <p>Authors from institutions that might limit the authors' ability to grant to AAAS any of the rights described in AAAS's license must obtain an approved waiver from their institution to publish with the Science Journal.</p> <p>Original research papers are freely accessible with registration on the Science Journal's website 12 months after publication.</p>

<p>Nature</p>	<p>https://www.nature.com/authors/policies/license.html#Self_archiving_policy</p>	<p><i>Nature Research's policies are compatible with the vast majority of funders' open access and self-archiving mandates.</i></p> <p>More information is available on the SHERPA/ROMEO website. Nature Research actively supports the self-archiving process, and continually works with authors, readers, subscribers and site-license holders to develop its policy.</p> <p>Preprints</p> <p>Nature Research journals support posting of primary research manuscripts on community preprint servers such as arXiv and bioRxiv. Preprint posting is not considered prior publication and will not jeopardize consideration at Nature Research journals. Preprints will not be considered when determining the conceptual advance provided by a study under consideration at Nature Research. Authors posting preprints are asked to respect our policy on communications with the media (http://www.nature.com/authors/policies/embargo.html). Our policy on posting and citation of preprints of primary research manuscripts is summarized below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The original submitted version of the manuscript (the version that has not undergone peer review) may be posted at any time. Authors should disclose details of preprint posting, including DOI, upon submission of the manuscript to a Nature Research journal. • For subscription journals, the Author's Accepted Manuscript (authors' accepted version of the manuscript) of the manuscript may only be posted 6 months after the paper is published, consistent with our self-archiving embargo (http://www.nature.com/authors/policies/license.html). Please note that the Author's Accepted Manuscript may not be released under a Creative Commons license. For Nature Research's Terms of Reuse of archived manuscripts please see: http://www.nature.com/authors/policies/license.html#terms • For subscription journals, the published PDF must not be posted on a preprint server or any other website. However, authors are encouraged to obtain a free SharedIt link of their paper, which can be posted online and allows read-only access. SharedIt links can be obtained by submitting the published article DOI at http://authors.springernature.com/share • Preprints may be cited in the reference list as below: • babichev, S.A., Ries, J. Lvovsky, A.I.
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		<p>Quantum scissors: teleportation of single-mode optical states by means of a nonlocal single photon. Preprint at http://arXiv.org/quant-ph/0208066 (2002).</p> <p>Author's Accepted Manuscript</p> <p>When a research paper is accepted for publication in an Nature Research journal, authors are encouraged to submit the Author's Accepted Manuscript to PubMedCentral or other appropriate funding body's archive, for public release six months after first publication. In addition, authors are encouraged to archive this version of the manuscript in their institution's repositories and, if they wish, on their personal websites, also six months after the original publication. Authors should cite the publication reference and <u>DOI number</u> on the first page of any deposited version, and provide a link from it to the URL of the published article on the journal's website. Where journals publish content online ahead of publication in a print issue (known as advanced online publication, or AOP), authors may make the archived version openly available six months after first online publication (AOP).</p> <p>Open access content</p> <p>For open access content published under a Creative Commons licence, the published version can be deposited immediately on publication, alongside a link to the URL of the published article on the journal's website. In all cases, the requirement to link to the journal's website is designed to protect the integrity and authenticity of the scientific record, with the online published version on nature.com clearly identified as the definitive version of record.</p> <p>Manuscript deposition service</p> <p>To facilitate self-archiving of original research papers and help authors fulfil funder and institutional mandates, Nature Research deposits manuscripts in PubMed Central, Europe PubMed Central and PubMed Central Canada on behalf of authors who opt-in to this free service during submission. (This service does not apply to Reviews or Protocols.) More information on the <u>Nature Research's Manuscript Deposition Service</u> is available. To take advantage of this service, the corresponding author must opt-in during the manuscript submission process. Corresponding authors should be mindful of all co-authors' self-archiving requirements.</p>
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From this list, we can see that the majority of the journals targeted by Q-SORT are scientific journals, which allow an open access modality and/or the author to deposit a post-print version in a repository such as arXiv¹². This is in line with the Horizon 2020 requirements.

All the publications will acknowledge the project's EU funding. This acknowledgment must be included also in the metadata of the generated information, since it allows to maximise the discoverability of publications and to ensure the acknowledgment of EU funding. The terms to be included in the metadata are:

- "European Union (EU)" and "Horizon 2020"
- the name of the action, the acronym of the project, and the grant number
- the publication date, length of embargo period if applicable, and a persistent identifier (e.g DOI, Handle)

Finally, in the Model Grant Agreement, "scientific publications" mean primarily journal articles. Whenever possible, Q-SORT will provide access to other types of scientific publications such as presentations, public deliverables, etc.

¹² <https://arxiv.org>

4 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Answers to the following questions help to achieve FAIR data.

4.1 WHAT ARE THE COSTS FOR MAKING DATA FAIR IN YOUR PROJECT? HOW WILL THESE BE COVERED?

NOTE THAT COSTS RELATED TO OPEN ACCESS TO RESEARCH DATA ARE ELIGIBLE AS PART OF THE HORIZON 2020 GRANT (IF COMPLIANT WITH THE GRANT AGREEMENT CONDITIONS)

The FAIR framework has a minimum impact on Q-SORT. The development and management of the Q-SORT open data/FAIR activities is incorporated into and budgeted for in the current Work Plan.

Overall data management will be undertaken by CNR.

The resources for long-term preservation are secured via Zenodo¹³ and in detail:

- **Versions:** *Data files are versioned. Records are not versioned. The uploaded data is archived as a Submission Information Package. Derivatives of data files are generated, but original content is never modified. Records can be retracted from public view; however, the data files and record are preserved.*
- **Replicas:** *All data files are stored in CERN Data Centres, primarily Geneva, with replicas in Budapest. Data files are kept in multiple replicas in a distributed file system, which is backed up to tape on a nightly basis.*
- **Retention period:** *Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.*
- **Functional preservation:** *Zenodo makes no promises of usability and understandability of deposited objects over time.*
- **File preservation:** *Data files and metadata are backed up nightly and replicated into multiple copies in the online system.*
- **Fixity and authenticity:** *All data files are stored along with a MD5 checksum of the file content. Files are regularly checked against their checksums to assure that file content remains constant.*
- **Succession plans:** *In case of closure of the repository, best efforts will be made to integrate all content into suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories.”*

4.2 WHO WILL BE RESPONSIBLE FOR DATA MANAGEMENT IN YOUR PROJECT?

CNR will be responsible as the Project Coordinator.

5 OPEN DATA SECURITY

Answers to the following questions help to achieve FAIR data.

5.1 WHAT PROVISIONS ARE IN PLACE FOR DATA SECURITY (INCLUDING DATA RECOVERY AS WELL AS SECURE STORAGE AND TRANSFER OF SENSITIVE DATA)?

Q-SORT stores the processed/parsed results into Zenodo.

Zenodo servers are managed via [OpenStack](#) and [Puppet](#) configuration management system which ensures that the servers always have the latest security patches applied¹⁴.

5.2 IS THE DATA SAFELY STORED IN CERTIFIED REPOSITORIES FOR LONG-TERM PRESERVATION AND CURATION?

Zenodo takes security very seriously. Its website reads:

¹³ <http://about.zenodo.org/policies/>

¹⁴ <http://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>

“CERN Data Centre: Zenodo’s data centres is located on CERN premises and all physical access is restricted to a limited number of staff with appropriate training and who have been granted access in line with their professional duties (e.g. Zendo staff do not have physical access to the CERN Data Centre) .

Servers: Zenodo’s servers are managed according to the CERN Security Baseline for Servers, meaning e.g. remote access to our servers are restricted to Zenodo staff with appropriate training, and the operating system and installed applications are kept updated with latest security patches via our automatic configuration management system Puppet.

Network: CERN Security Team runs both host and network based intrusion detection systems and monitors the traffic flow, pattern and contents into and out of CERN networks in order to detect attacks. All access to zenodo.org happens over HTTPS, except for static documentation pages which are hosted on GitHub Pages.

Data: Zenodo stores user passwords using strong cryptographic password hashing algorithms (currently PBKDF2+SHA512). Users’ access tokens to GitHub and ORCID are stored encrypted and can only be decrypted with the application’s secret key.

Application: Zenodo employees a suite of techniques to protect session from being stolen by an attacker when logged in and run vulnerability scans against the application.

Staff: CERN staff with access to user data operate under [CERN Operational Circular no. 5](#), meaning among other things that

- staff should not exchange among themselves information acquired unless it is expressly required for the execution of their duties.*
- access to user data must always be consistent with the professional duties and only permitted for resolution of problems, detection of security issues, monitoring of resources and similar.*
- staff are liable for damage resulting from any infringement and can have access withdrawn and/or be subject to disciplinary or legal proceedings depending on seriousness of the infringement.”*

6 ETHICAL ASPECTS

Answers to the following questions help to achieve FAIR data.

6.1 ARE THERE ANY ETHICAL OR LEGAL ISSUES THAT CAN HAVE AN IMPACT ON DATA SHARING? THESE CAN ALSO BE DISCUSSED IN THE CONTEXT OF THE ETHICS REVIEW.

The Q-SORT Consortium has not identified any specific ethics issues related to the Work Plan, outcomes or dissemination.

7 LIST OF Q-SORT DATA SETS, PRE-PRINTS, ARTICLES, DELIVERABLES PUBLISHED ON ZENODO

Data sets

1) Application of the OAM sorter to incident beams having different value of orbital angular momentum

Tavabi, Amir; Rosi, Paolo; Peng-Han, Lu; Gazzadi, Gian Carlo; Frabboni, Stefano; Dunin-Borkowski, Rafal; Grillo, Vincenzo

This dataset contains the characterization of an OAM sorter. The sorter has been tested inside the TEM and has been illuminated with vortex beams having different topological charge (as encoded in the filename).

2) Generation of vortex beams with large OAM

Peng-Han, Lu; Paolo, Rosi; Tavabi, Amir; Gazzadi, Gian Carlo; Grillo, Vincenzo; Frabboni, Stefano; Dunin-Borkowski, Rafal

This dataset contains TEM micrographs of custom apertures realized on Au-coated SiN membranes via FIB milling used for the realization of electron beams with large OAM ($l = 500$ and $l = 1000$).

3) TEM holography characterization of the first element of the fan-out sorter

Grillo, Vincenzo; Rosi, Paolo; Gazzadi, Gian Carlo; Frabboni, Stefano; Tavabi, Amir; Lu, Peng-Han; Dunin Borkowski, Rafal

This dataset contains the phase reconstruction of the first element of an OAM sorter. The phase mask has been realized in the fan-out configuration via FIB milling of a thin SiN membrane. The reconstruction is obtained via TEM holography experiments.

4) Test of a sorter for different OAM value of the incident beam

Rosi, Paolo; Tavabi, Amir; Gazzadi, Gian Carlo; Lu, Peng-Han; Grillo, Vincenzo; Frabboni, Stefano; Dunin-Borkowski, Rafal

In this dataset a fan-out version of the OAM sorter has been tested inside the TEM. The sorter has been illuminated with vortex beams having different topological charge (as encoded in the filename).

5) Characterization of a sorter1 hologram

Balboni, Roberto; Rosi, Paolo; Gian Carlo Gazzadi; Grillo, Vincenzo; Frabboni, Stefano

This dataset contains a series of TEM images characterizing a fan-out version of the first element of an OAM sorter.

Pre-prints:

1) Structured Quantum Projectiles

Larocque, Hugo; Fickler, Robert; Cohen, Eliahu; Grillo, Vincenzo; Dunin-Borkowski, Rafal; Leuchs, Gerd; Karimi, Ebrahim

2) Generation of electron vortices using non-exact electric fields

Tavabi, Amir H.; Larocque, Hugo; Lu, Peng-Han; Duchamp, Martial; Grillo, Vincenzo; Karimi, Ebrahim; Dunin-Borkowski, Rafal; Pozzi, Giulio

3) Electron beam shaping: how to control the e-beam propagation along atomic columns

Rotunno, Enzo; Tavabi, Amir; Yucelen, Emrah; Frabboni, Stefano; Dunin-Borkowski, Rafal; Karimi, Ebrahim; McMorran, Benjamin J.

4) Generation and control of an ultrafast electron vortex beam via chiral plasmonic near - fields

Vanacore, Giovanni Maria; Berruto, Gabriele; Madan, Ivan; Pomarico, Enrico; Biagioni, Paolo; Lamb, R.J.; Reinhardt, O.; Kaminer, Ido; Barwick, I; Larocque, Hugo; Grillo, Vincenzo; Karimi, Ebrahim; Garcia de Abajo, F.J.; Carbone, Fabrizio

Deliverables

1) Project deliverable

D6.1 Project Website and Logo

2) Project deliverable

D1.10 Open Data Management Plan (First release)

3) Project deliverable

D2.2 Report about working holographic sorter configuration

4) Project deliverable

D1.2 International Conference Proceedings (Release 1)

5) Project deliverable

D5.1 Report on integration of cryo-blades and cryo-imaging into the Titan-Holo microscope at FZJ (release 1)

8 CONCLUSION

This first release of the Open Data Management Plan specifies the principles and actions that Q-SORT will embrace in order to make most of its data FAIR.

Q-SORT will revisit the Open Data Management Plan in the following two releases, which will be updated -if necessary- according to any need which might arise as a consequence of the actions and activities undertaken to achieve the objectives of the project.

ANNEX 1 - EXPERIMENTAL DATA SET SPECIFICATIONS

Data set description	Q-SORT data sets will comprise the measured or simulated images, spectra or spectral image obtained with the electron microscope.
File format	Preferential format is Dm3 Gatan format
Standards and metadata	Metadata is based on ZENODO's metadata, which includes the title, creator, date, contributor, description, keywords, format, resource type, etc.
Data sharing	These data sets will be available under CC BY-NC-SA license and will be deposited in the ZENODO repository. In order to analyse this data, Digital Micrograph, ImageJ, or Stem_cell software are required.
Archiving and preservation	These data sets will be archived and preserved in ZENODO.

ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd.	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Maastricht MultiModal Molecular Imaging Institute	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL